
JupyterFAIR

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FAIRLY PACKAGE

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INSTALLATION

Fairly is a Python package that provides functionality for the core tasks of preparing, uploading and downloading datasets from research data repositories. The package currently provides integration with [Zenodo](#) and [Figshare](#) repositories such as [4TU.ResearchData](#)

1.1 Installing using Pip

The easier way to install *fairly* is using *pip*, it requires Python 3.8 or later.

On the terminal type:

```
pip install fairly
```

1.2 Installing from Source

Installing *fairly* from source requires *setuptools* version 49.0 or later and *pip*.

1. Clone or download the [source code](#):

```
git clone https://github.com/ITC-CRIB/fairly.git
```

2. Unzip if necessary, and move to the root directory:

```
cd fairly/
```

3. Compile and install by doing:

```
pip install .
```

Note: Currently, the package only supports the [Zenodo](#) and [4TU.ResearchData](#) repositories. For more details on how to use *fairly* and some examples, see the **Quick Start** section.

DOWNLOAD DATASETS FROM 4TU.RESEARCHDATA

fairly can download public datasets from 4TU.ResearchData. The *4TU.ResearchData* repository uses Figshare as a platform for managing research datasets. For this example, we will use the dataset [EDoM measurement campaign](#). This dataset contains 28 files of different types (.txt, .pdf), and it is about 278 MBs in size.

The dataset has ID: 20308263, in 4TU.ResearchData the dataset ID is the last part of the URL that appears in the web browser. We can fetch a dataset using either its ID or its URL.

2.1 1. Connect to 4TU.ResearchData

To connect to data repositories we use clients. A client manage the connection to an specific data repository. We can create a client to connect to 4TU.ReseachData as follows:

```
[4]: import fairly

fourtu = fairly.client("4tu")
```

2.2 2. Connect to a dataset

Now, we can connect to a *public* dataset by calling the `get_dataset()` method and using either the dataset ID or its URL, or the DOI.

```
[5]: # USING ID
# dataset = fourtu.get_dataset("20308263")

# USING URL
dataset = fourtu.get_dataset("https://data.4tu.nl/articles/dataset/EDoM_measurement_
↳campaign_full_data_from_the_lower_Ems_River/20308263")

# COMVENIENT FUNCTION, USING DOI
# dataset = fairly.dataset( https://doi.org/10.4121/19519618.v1) # client is infered_
↳from DOI
```

2.3 3. Explore dataset's metadata

Once we have made a connection to a dataset, we can access its metadata (as stored in the data repository) by using the metadata property.

```
[3]: # Retrieves metadata from data repository
dataset.metadata

[3]: Metadata({'authors': [Person({'fullname': 'Bas van Maren', 'orcid_id': '0000-0001-5820-
→3212', 'figshare_id': 11844539}), Person({'fullname': 'Andreas Engels', 'figshare_id':
→12901508})], 'keywords': ['Hydrodynamics', 'Sediment dynamics', 'Collection: The Ems-
→Dollard Measurement (EDoM) campaign'], 'description': '<p>A large amount of long term
→monitoring data collected during the Edom measurement campaign has been published in
→Net CDF as part of the collection \'Edom measurements campaign: data from long-term
→monitoring\' ( <a href="https://doi.org/10.4121/19519618.v1" target="_blank">https://
→doi.org/10.4121/19519618.v1</a>). This dataset provides the full subset of the long
→term mooring data (including oxygen and flow velocities) in ASCII text format, and
→only for the lower Ems River</p>', 'license': 'CC BY-NC-SA 4.0', 'title': 'EDoM
→measurement campaign: full data from the lower Ems River', 'doi': '10.4121/20308263.v1
→', 'type': 'dataset', 'access_type': 'open', 'custom_fields': {'Publisher': '4TU.
→ResearchData', 'Language': '', 'Time coverage': '2017-2019', 'Geolocation': 'Ems
→estuary', 'Geolocation Longitude': '7.04', 'Geolocation Latitude': '53.30', 'Format':
→'ASCII text', 'Data Link': [], 'Derived From': [], 'Same As': [], 'Organizations':
→'Niedersächsischer Landesbetrieb für Wasserwirtschaft Küsten (NLWKN);'}, 'embargo_type
→': 'file', 'categories': ['Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience'], 'online_
→date': '2022-07-14T10:56:04', '4tu_id': {'id': '20308263', 'version': None}})
```

2.4 4. List dataset's files

We can list the files of a dataset using the files property. The result is a Python dictionary where the name of each file becomes elements of the dictionary.

```
[4]: # Lists files (data) associated to the dataset
files = dataset.files

print("There are", len(files), "files in this dataset")

print(files)

There are 28 files in this dataset
{'CsEmpsper_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'CsEmpsper_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.
→txt', 'CsGandesum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'CsGandesum_01052017-01052019_
→from_NLWKN.txt', 'CsKnock_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'CsKnock_01052017-
→01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'CsMP1_01052017-01052019_from_WSV.txt': 'CsMP1_01052017-
→01052019_from_WSV.txt', 'CsPogum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'CsPogum_01052017-
→01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'CsTerborg_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'CsTerborg_
→01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'Messung_Gewaesserguete_EMS_NLWKN.pdf': 'Messung_
→Gewaesserguete_EMS_NLWKN.pdf', 'O2Empsper_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt':
→'O2Empsper_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'O2Gandesum_01052017-01052019_from_
→NLWKN.txt': 'O2Gandesum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'O2Knock_01052017-01052019_
→from_NLWKN.txt': 'O2Knock_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'O2MP1_01052017-01052019_
→from_WSV.txt': 'O2MP1_01052017-01052019_from_WSV.txt', 'O2Pogum_01052017-01052019_from_
```

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```

↪NLWKN.txt': 'O2Pogum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'O2Terborg_01052017-01052019_
↪from_NLWKN.txt': 'O2Terborg_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'Q_Versen_052017-052019.
↪txt': 'Q_Versen_052017-052019.txt', 'readme.txt': 'readme.txt', 'SpEmpsier_01052017-
↪01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'SpEmpsier_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt', 'SpGandersum_
↪01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'SpGandersum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt',
↪'SpKnock_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'SpKnock_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt',
↪'SpMP1_01052017-01052019_from_WSV.txt': 'SpMP1_01052017-01052019_from_WSV.txt',
↪'SpPogum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'SpPogum_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt',
↪'SpTerborg_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt': 'SpTerborg_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.
↪txt', 'U_Emden_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt': 'U_Emden_01052017-01052019_from_
↪WSA_Emden.txt', 'U_Knock_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt': 'U_Knock_01052017-
↪01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt', 'U_MP1_01052017-01052019_from_WSV.txt': 'U_MP1_01052017-
↪01052019_from_WSV.txt', 'U_Terborg_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt': 'U_Terborg_
↪01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt', 'WL_Emden_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt':
↪'WL_Emden_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt', 'WL_Knock_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_
↪Emden.txt': 'WL_Knock_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt', 'WL_Terborg_01052017-
↪01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt': 'WL_Terborg_01052017-01052019_from_WSA_Emden.txt'}

```

2.5 5. Download a file

We can download a single file in a dataset by using its name. For example, this dataset contains a file with the name 'CsEmpsier_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt'.

The path parameter can be used to define where to store the file, otherwise the file will be stored in the working directory.

```

[5]: # Select a file from the dataset
single_file = dataset.files['CsEmpsier_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt']

# download the file
fourtu.download_file(single_file)

[5]: 'CsEmpsier_01052017-01052019_from_NLWKN.txt'

```

2.6 6. Download a dataset

We can download all files and metadata of a dataset using the `store()` function. We need to provide a path to a directory to store the dataset. If the directory does not exist, it would be created.

```

[6]: # This will download about 278 MBs
dataset.store("./edom")

[6]: <fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset at 0x7f143af8a6b0>

```


DOWNLOAD DATASETS FROM ZENODO

fairly can also download public datasets from Zenodo. The *Zenodo* repository has its own platform for managing research datasets. For this example, we will use the dataset [Quality and timing of crowd-based water level class observations](#). This dataset is a single compressed file of type `.zip`, which contains several other files and directories, and it is about 27 MBs in size.

In Zenodo the ID of a dataset can be found by looking at its DOI. The last part of a DOI (a number). For example, the DOI for the second version of the dataset is `10.5281/zenodo.3929547`, therefore its ID is `3929547`. We can fetch a dataset using either its ID or its URL.

3.1 1. Connect to Zenodo

To connect to data repositories we use clients. A client manages the connection to a specific data repository. We can create a client to connect to Zenodo as follows:

```
[7]: import fairly

zenodo = fairly.client(id="zenodo")
```

3.2 2. Connect to a dataset

Now, we can connect to a *public* dataset by calling the `get_dataset()` method and using either the dataset ID or its URL.

```
[8]: # USING ID
dataset = zenodo.get_dataset("3929547")

# USING URL
dataset = zenodo.get_dataset("https://zenodo.org/record/3929547#.Yw_SodJBxhF")
```

3.3 3. Explore dataset's metadata

Once we have made a connection to a dataset, we can access its metadata (as stored in the data repository) by calling the metadata property of a dataset.

```
[9]: # Retrieves metadata from data repository
dataset.metadata

[9]: Metadata({'type': 'dataset', 'publication_date': '2020-02-20', 'title': 'Data and R-
↳Scripts for "Quality and timing of crowd-based water level class observations"',
↳'authors': [Person({'fullname': 'Etter, Simon', 'institution': 'University of Zurich,
↳Department of Geography', 'orcid_id': '0000-0002-7553-9102', 'name': 'Simon', 'surname
↳': 'Etter'})], Person({'fullname': 'Strobl, Barbara', 'institution': 'University of
↳Zurich, Department of Geography', 'orcid_id': '0000-0001-5530-4632', 'name': 'Barbara',
↳'surname': 'Strobl'})], Person({'fullname': 'Seibert, Jan', 'institution': 'University
↳of Zurich, Department of Geography', 'orcid_id': '0000-0002-6314-2124', 'name': 'Jan',
↳'surname': 'Seibert'})], Person({'fullname': 'van Meerveld, Ilja (H.J.)', 'institution':
↳'University of Zurich, Department of Geography', 'orcid_id': '0000-0002-7547-3270',
↳'name': 'Ilja (H.J.)', 'surname': 'van Meerveld'})], 'description': '<p>This are the
↳data and the R-scripts used for the manuscript &quot;Quality and timing of crowd-based
↳water level class observations&quot; accepted for publication in the journal
↳Hydrological Processes in July 2020 as a Scientific Briefing. To run the code, just
↳run the R-script with the name &quot;RunThisForResults.R&quot;. Results will be
↳written to the &quot;Figures&quot; and the &quot;Results&quot; folder.</p>', 'access_
↳type': 'open', 'license': 'CC-BY-4.0', 'doi': '10.5281/zenodo.3929547', 'keywords': [
↳'CrowdWater', 'Hydrology'], 'zenodo_id': {'id': '3929547'}, 'prereserve_doi': {'doi':
↳'10.5281/zenodo.3929547', 'recid': '3929547'}, 'related_identifiers': [{'identifier':
↳'10.5281/zenodo.3676350', 'relation': 'isVersionOf', 'scheme': 'doi'}], 'grants': ['10.
↳13039/501100001711::200021_163008'], 'version': '2', 'language': 'eng'})
```

3.4 4. List dataset's files

We can list the files of a dataset using the files property. The result is a Python dictionary where the name of each file is an element of the dictionary. In this case the dataset contains only one file.

```
[10]: # Lists files (data) associated to the dataset
files = dataset.files

print("There are", len(files), "files in this dataset")

print(files)

There are 1 files in this dataset
{'DataForUploadToZenodo.zip': 'DataForUploadToZenodo.zip'}
```

3.5 5. Download a file

We can download the file in the dataset by using the name of a file. For example 'DataForUploadToZenodo.zip'.

The path parameter can be used to define where to store the file, otherwise the file will be store in the working directory.

```
[5]: # Select a file to download from the dataset
single_file = dataset.files['DataForUploadToZenodo.zip'] # missing updating the manifest

# download a file
zenodo.download_file(single_file, path="./from-zenodo")

[5]: 'DataForUploadToZenodo.zip'
```

3.6 6. Download a dataset

We also can download all files and metadata of a dataset using the store() function. We need to provide a path to a directory to store the dataset. If the directory does not exist, it would be created.

```
[11]: # This will download about 278 MBs
dataset.store("./quality") # use extract=True for unzipping

[11]: <fairly.dataset.local.LocalDataset at 0x7f5250515ba0>
```


CONFIGURING ACCESS TOKEN

fairly can be used to access datasets owned by a user of a data repository. For 4TU.ReaseachData and Zenodo, we can do data by configuring access tokens.

4.1 Creating a personal access token

A personal access token allows to connect to a user account remotely without the need to a *username* and *password*.

4.1.1 Zenodo

1. Register for a Zenodo account if you do not already have one.
2. Go to your *Applications*, and click on *New token* under **Personal access tokens**.
3. Enter a name for your token.
4. Select the OAuth scopes you need (*deposit:write* and *deposit:actions*).
5. Click *Create*
6. An access token will be showned, copy it and store it. **The token will only be showned once.**
7. Click on *Save*

4.1.2 4TU.ReaseachData

1. Register for a Zenodo account if you do not already have one.
2. Go to your *Applications*, and click on *Create Personal Token*.
3. Enter short description for your token, for example a name, and click on *Save*
4. An access token will be showned, copy it and store it. **The token will only be showned once.**
5. Click on *Done*

4.2 Connecting to an Account

Connecting to an account is as simple as passign a token when creating a 4TU.ResearchDaata or Zenodo client.

```
from fairly import client

# For 4TU.ReseachData
fourtu = client(id="figshare", token="<my-tu-token>" )

# For Zenodo
fourtu = client(id="zenodo", token="<my-zenodo-token>" )
```

4.3 Storing Tokens

To store your Tokens, create a JSON file like the one below and store it at `~/.fairly/repositories.json` You can store tokens for other repositories by adding them to this file as “<repository-ID>”: {“token”: <the-token>}

```
{
  "4tu": {
    "token": "<4tu-token>"
  }
}
```

ACCESS ACCOUNT DATASETS

With *fairly*, you can access the datasets in a repository's user account. This tutorial shows you the how to, for the case of 4TU.ResearchData. The procedure is the same for Zenodo.

Requirements:

- A 4TU.ReseachData account
- A personal access token. See [configuring access token](#) if you don't have one.

5.1 1. Connect to an account

To connect to an repository's account, we need pass a personal token when creating a client. Or we can store tokens in a configuration file at `~/.fairly/repositories.json`

```
[3]: # Passing a token directly
import fairly

fourtu = fairly.client(id="figshare", token="<4tu-token>")
```

To store your Tokens, create a JSON file like the one below and store it at `~/.fairly/repositories.json` You can store tokens for other repositories by adding them to this file as `"<repository-ID>": {"token": <the-token>}`

```
{
  "4tu": {
    "token": "<4tu-token>"
  }
}
```

5.2 2. Retrieve account datasets

You can see the datasets in an account by calling the `get_account_datasets()` function; this retrieves a list of dataset in an account. Then, you can use the `id` and `metadata` properties of a *dataset* to find more details.

```
[4]: # retrieves the datasets in an account
my_datasets = fourtu.get_account_datasets()

# # check the number of dataets in an account
```

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```
print ("There are", len(my_datasets), "datasets in this account")
```

```
There are 2 datasets in this account
```

```
[5]: print("Dataset Ids:")
```

```
## print the IDs
```

```
print([dataset.id for dataset in my_datasets])
```

```
Dataset Ids:
```

```
[{'id': '20758348', 'version': None}, {'id': '20752675', 'version': None}]
```

```
[6]: # metadata for first dataset
```

```
my_datasets[0].metadata
```

```
[6]: Metadata({'authors': [Person({'fullname': 'Manuel Garcia Alvarez', 'figshare_id': '10645703'})], 'license': 'CC BY 4.0', 'title': 'test-dataset', 'type': 'software', 'access_type': 'open', 'custom_fields': {'Publisher': '4TU.ResearchData', 'Language': ''}, 'Time coverage': '', 'Geolocation': '', 'Geolocation Longitude': '', 'Geolocation Latitude': '', 'Format': '', 'Data Link': [], 'Derived From': [], 'Same As': [], 'Organizations': ''}, 'embargo_type': 'file', 'categories': ['Communications Technologies'], 'figshare_id': {'id': '20758348', 'version': None}})
```

ARCHIVING DATASET

With **fairly**, we can remotely archive and edit datasets in a user account. Users can prepare a dataset for archiving by editing metadata, defining which files are part of a dataset, and uploading them to a data repository. One of the purposes of **fairly** is to *remove the need of preparing metadata and data for every repository to which a dataset will be archived*. Therefore, saving time and effort, and lowering the barriers for practicing open science. This tutorial shows what is possible using the 4TU.ResearchData repository. The procedure is similar for Zenodo.

Requirements:

- A 4TU.ReseachData account
- A personal access token. See [configuring access token](#) if you don't have one.
- Files to be archived. We will use a hypothetical case in this tutorial.

For this totorial, we assume that our goal is to archive a dataset in 4TU.ResearchData, that we previously archived in Zenodo. We will use the dataset [Quality and timing of crowd-based water level class observations](#), as an example.

6.1 1. Download the Zenodo dataset

First, we need to download the [Quality and timing of crowd-based water level class observations](#), using its URL. If you did this in the tutorial about *downloading datasets from Zenoso*, you can skip this step.

```
[3]: import fairly

# create a zenodo client
zenodo = fairly.client(id="zenodo")

## connect and download a zenodo dataset
source_dataset = zenodo.get_dataset("https://zenodo.org/record/3929547#.YxAeJNJBxhF")
source_dataset.store("./quality/")
```

6.2 2. Editing Metadata

Now we can load the downloaded dataset, and we could edit the metadata of a dataset as following. For example, we can add a few more *keywords* and edit the *license*.

```
[4]: import fairly

# Load a previously downloaded by passing a path to a directory.
local_dataset = fairly.dataset("./quality/") # load from local dataset

# zenodo dataset metadata
print(local_dataset.metadata)

{'access_type': 'open', 'authors': [Person({'fullname': 'Etter, Simon', 'institution':
↳ 'University of Zurich, Department of Geography', 'name': 'Simon', 'orcid_id': '0000-
↳ 0002-7553-9102', 'surname': 'Etter'}), Person({'fullname': 'Strobl, Barbara',
↳ 'institution': 'University of Zurich, Department of Geography', 'name': 'Barbara',
↳ 'orcid_id': '0000-0001-5530-4632', 'surname': 'Strobl'})], Person({'fullname': 'Seibert,
↳ Jan', 'institution': 'University of Zurich, Department of Geography', 'name': 'Jan',
↳ 'orcid_id': '0000-0002-6314-2124', 'surname': 'Seibert'}), Person({'fullname': 'van
↳ Meerveld, Ilja (H.J.)', 'institution': 'University of Zurich, Department of Geography',
↳ 'name': 'Ilja (H.J.)', 'orcid_id': '0000-0002-7547-3270', 'surname': 'van Meerveld'}
↳)], 'description': '<p>This are the data and the R-scripts used for the manuscript &
↳ quot;Quality and timing of crowd-based water level class observations&quot; accepted
↳ for publication in the journal Hydrological Processes in July 2020 as a Scientific
↳ Briefing. To run the code, just run the R-script with the name &quot;RunThisForResults.
↳ R&quot;. Results will be written to the &quot;Figures&quot; and the &quot;Results&quot;
↳ folder.</p>', 'doi': '10.5281/zenodo.3929547', 'grants': ['10.13039/501100001711::
↳ 200021_163008'], 'keywords': ['CrowdWater', 'Hydrology'], 'language': 'eng', 'license':
↳ 'CC-BY-4.0', 'prereserve_doi': {'doi': '10.5281/zenodo.3929547', 'recid': 3929547},
↳ 'publication_date': '2020-02-20', 'related_identifiers': [{'identifier': '10.5281/
↳ zenodo.3676350', 'relation': 'isVersionOf', 'scheme': 'doi'}], 'title': 'Data and R-
↳ Scripts for "Quality and timing of crowd-based water level class observations"', 'type
↳ ': 'dataset', 'version': '2', 'zenodo_id': {'id': '3929547'}}
```

```
[5]: # edit keywords
local_dataset.metadata["keywords"] = ["CrowdWater", "Hydrology", "made by fairly"]

# Edit the license name to match what is required by 4TU.ResearchData.
local_dataset.metadata["license"] = "CC BY 4.0"
```

6.3 3. Archive to 4TU.ResearchData

Now we can create a new dataset in an 4TU.ResearchData account, by doing the following. We assume a **Personal access token** has already been added to `~/fairly/repositories.json`

```
[6]: local_dataset.upload("figshare", notify=fairly.notify)

DataForUploadToZenodo.zip, 26765942/10485760
DataForUploadToZenodo.zip, 26765942/20971520
DataForUploadToZenodo.zip, 26765942/26765942
```

```
[6]: <fairly.dataset.remote.RemoteDataset at 0x7f62f5326200>
```

We could continue uploading files or editing the metadata in a similar way. For now, **publishing** the dataset should be done via the web interface of 4TU.ResearchData.

USING THE CLI

Important: This feature is currently under development. For the latest version of *fairly* visit the [project repository](#). Consider contributing to this open source project by reporting and fixing bugs, or implementing features.

USING THE EXTENSION

Important: This feature is currently under development. For the latest version of *fairly* visit the [project repository](#). Consider contributing to this open source project by reporting and fixing bugs, or implementing features.
